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Translation, cultural adaptation, and validation of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic: a self-rated ICF-based questionnaire for assessing hearing, communication, and conversation disability in Arabic-speaking populations

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Abstract

Background The HEAR-COMMAND Tool is a self-reported questionnaire designed to assess hearing, communication, and conversation functioning (aka negative: disability), based on the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) Core Sets for Hearing Loss. This study aims to introduce the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic to healthcare professionals in Arabic-speaking regions. It will provide them with a reliable and culturally relevant instrument that aligns with the ICF framework. Grounded in ICF, this tool represents a significant advancement in hearing-related assessment within the Arab world.

Methods The study was conducted in the Department of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery, Audio-vestibular Medicine Division at Sohag University Hospital, Sohag, Egypt. The translation process followed a rigorous, multi-step approach to ensure linguistic accuracy and cultural relevance. This process included forward translation, expert panel review, and back translation. Content validation of the initial (beta) version was performed to confirm the tool's relevance and comprehensibility by collecting responses from 30 participants. After implementing the suggested revisions, the revised version was provided to another cohort of 52 participants, including individuals with mild to moderately severe hearing loss and those with normal hearing, to evaluate the tool's reliability and validity. Statistical analyses were conducted to assess internal consistency and content validity, ensuring the tool's robustness for use in Arabic-speaking populations.

Results The content validity analysis of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic demonstrated a strong prevalence of impairment related to auditory functions, with auditory perception (80%-100%), sound detection (80%-100%), and speech discrimination (80%-100%) being highly represented. The tool also effectively captured several moderate prevalence challenges (50%-79%), including attention, memory, emotional regulation, social participation, and communication difficulties. It emphasized the impact of social determinants and environmental factors, such as sound quality and infrastructure compatibility, in shaping communication outcomes. The reliability assessment showed high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.97).

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Conclusion The validation and reliability assessment revealed that the tool is a robust measure for self-reported hearing impairment and its associated daily functioning difficulties in the most populous country in the Arab Region. Additional validation of the tool through a multicenter study across other Arabic-speaking countries is strongly recommended.

Keywords Audiological Rehabilitation, Everyday Functioning, Hearing Loss, International Classification of Functioning Disability and Health, Patient-Reported Outcome Measures, HEAR-COMMAND Tool

Introduction

Disabling hearing loss (HL) is a widespread public health issue affecting individuals across various age groups, including early middle age (35–44 years), late middle age (45–64 years), and late adulthood (65 years and older) [1, 2]. According to the World Health Organization, disabling HL is a hearing threshold greater than 20 decibels (dB) in the better-hearing ear [1, 2]. Currently, over 1.5 billion people – nearly 20% of the global population – live with some degree of hearing loss, of whom 430 million experience disabling HL. By 2050, this number is projected to exceed 700 million, meaning 1 in every 10 individuals worldwide will be affected by disabling HL [1, 2].

Addressing disability-related HL in Arabic-speaking Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) countries remains challenging due to inconsistent data reporting and varying definitions of the disorder, which complicate accurate assessments of its prevalence and incidence [3, 4]. Recent estimates suggest that disabling HL affects between 10.8% and 15.9% of the population across these regions, except for Egypt, where the prevalence is reported at 7.7% [5, 6].

For individuals with disabling HL, diminished auditory abilities, especially in adults and the elderly, can profoundly impact daily functioning across the home, work, and social or business settings [7, 8]. To fully understand the implications of HL, it is essential to adopt the “functioning” perspective outlined in the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) Core Sets for HL, which promote a holistic approach to rehabilitation and care [9–18]. These core sets offer a comprehensive view of how HL impacts communication, social participation, and daily activities, guiding clinicians and researchers in evaluating functional limitations and disability in individuals with HL [9–18]. Accordingly, audiologic evaluation goes beyond audiological impairment to consider the broader effects of HL on emotional well-being, cognitive abilities, independence, and social participation. It also accounts for co-occurring bodily impairments and environmental factors, such as vision, mobility, and social support, which can exacerbate challenges like speech intelligibility in noisy environments [9–18].

Traditionally, hearing healthcare services have adopted a unidimensional view of rehabilitation, focusing largely on technological interventions such as hearing aids [8]. Although these solutions represent a critical initial step in the management of HL, this narrow focus fails to address the broader needs of individuals. Based on the ICF concepts, a hearing disability exists on a continuum, ranging from no disability (full functioning) to severe disability (very poor functioning) [19, 20]. This continuum highlights that the degree of disability cannot be determined solely by health conditions, fostering a balanced view of disabilities resulting from both physical and mental health conditions. Such considerations are particularly relevant in Arabic-speaking MENA countries, where disabling HL, alongside visual impairments, mobility challenges, cognitive difficulties, self-care issues, and communication barriers, represents one of the most prevalent types of disabilities [5, 6]. Hence, there is an urgent need to address the multifaceted impact of HL through a “functioning” perspective, highlighting the importance of a biopsychosocial approach to hearing healthcare in Arabic-speaking countries.

Noteworthy, the ICF Core Sets for HL paved the way for tools like the HEAR-COMMAND, a self-rated questionnaire designed to tailor interventions to the unique challenges individuals face in hearing, daily functioning, communication, and conversation, ultimately to enhance the patient-centeredness of audiological services, treatment, and rehabilitation for adults with HL [21, 22]. The different language versions can be accessed at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15234758>. Comprising 120 items, it includes 90 items focused on functioning and 30 items covering demographic details, hearing status, and personal factors. The tool aligns with 85% of the categories in the Brief ICF Core Set for HL. All the categories in this Core Set are addressed, except those in the Body Structure domain. Moreover, 44% of the Comprehensive ICF Core Set categories encompass 73% of Body Functions, 55% of Activities and Participation, and 27% of Environmental Factors domains. Developed by a multinational team from Germany, the USA, the Netherlands, and Egypt, it is available in English, German, and Arabic, ensuring its relevance across diverse linguistic and cultural settings [21, 22].

A prior cross-sectional multicenter study involving 215 participants from Germany, the USA, and Egypt tested the HEAR-COMMAND Tool, with responses provided in German, English, or Arabic. The findings revealed high content and construct validity, affirming the tool's effectiveness in capturing patients' perspectives on HL and its impact on hearing-related functioning. This robust validation supports its potential to enhance treatment planning and audiologic rehabilitation by offering a comprehensive assessment of daily hearing challenges and their effects on patients' functioning and quality of life [21, 22].

This paper presents the translation and content validation of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic, which enhances clinicians' ability to collect meaningful data on disability and ultimately improves patient-centered care in audiology and communication disorders in Arabic-speaking regions.

Materials and methods

Design

For details regarding the development of the English version, refer to Afghah et al., 2022 [21]. The focus of this paper is solely on the development and validation of the Arabic version. This study was conducted at the Audio-vestibular Medicine Division, Department of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery, Sohag University Hospitals, Egypt. The study received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Sohag University (registration number: Soh-Med-22–9-04).

The development of the Arabic version adhered to a rigorous seven-step methodology to ensure linguistic accuracy, cultural relevance, and conceptual equivalence. This process followed the WHO (2010) guidelines for translating the Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 [23] and best practices for adapting hearing-related questionnaires across languages and cultures [24].

- Preparation.** The translation process was systematically planned, and translators were provided with relevant background information about the tool, its purpose, and its intended use.
- Forward Translation.** The HEAR-COMMAND Tool – English was translated into Arabic by native Arabic speakers fluent in English and who have expertise in audiology terminology and translation.
- Cross-checking the Forward Translation.** The initial Arabic translation was independently reviewed by the Sohag Language and Translation Center at Sohag University, Egypt. This center specializes in language translation and provides certified services to ensure the accuracy and refinement of the translated version.

- Committee Review.** The authors compared and discussed the translations, resolving any discrepancies to create the Beta Version of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic.
- Pre-testing and Feedback.** A total of 30 participants with varying degrees of pure-tone average (PTA) and hearing aid experience were recruited from the Audiology Unit within the Otorhinolaryngology Department at the Faculty of Medicine, Sohag University, Egypt. Participant characteristics are detailed in Table 1. Recruitment was performed with and without consideration of the participant's knowledge of the cause of their HL or the previous clinical diagnostics. The respondents were asked to fill in the questionnaire and provide their feedback on the items either in writing or verbally during the cognitive interview. They were asked to identify the items that were found to be unclear, ambiguous, not meaningful, potentially have more than one meaning, or difficult to grade.
- Review and Refinement.** The authors evaluated the feedback and refined the Beta Version of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic accordingly.
- Field Testing and Validation Process:** The data were collected from 52 participants with varying degrees of PTA and hearing aid experience. They were recruited from the Audiology Unit within the Otorhinolaryngology Department at the Faculty of Medicine, Sohag University, Egypt. Participant characteristics are also detailed in Table 1. The participants were provided with the revised Version of the HEAR-

Table 1 The main demographic characteristics of the respondents in the translation phase

Characteristics	Translation Phase N=30	Validation Phase N=52
Gender	Male=5 Female=25	Male=23 Female=29
Age	Range=16–72 M±SD=42.9±18.1	Range=20–70 M±SD=39.61±15.69
Education (years)	M±SD=13.3±5.2	M±SD=15.85±2.14
Medical diagnosis (Co-morbid health conditions)	Yes=11 ^a No=19	Yes=15 ^a No=36
Hearing status:		
• Normal hearing	N=4	N=9
• Hearing impaired, Aided	N=9	N=11
• Hearing impaired, Unaided	N=17	N=32
Pure-Tone Average (dB HL)	Range=9–55 M±SD=40.5±12.79	Range=10–55 M±SD=34.23±14.5

^a Cardiac-metabolic syndrome

COMMAND Tool – Arabic from Oct 2022 to Aug 2023 in pencil-and-paper format. Recruitment was performed with and without consideration of the participant's knowledge of the cause of their HL or the previous clinical diagnostics. On average, it takes approximately 15–20 min to complete the questionnaire.

Statistical data analysis

Content validity was evaluated through quantitative analysis using descriptive statistics. The reliability of the tool was assessed by measuring internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficient used to determine the consistency of the items within the questionnaire. The dataset was analyzed using MATLAB R2021b and IBM's Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25.

Results

Content validity, qualitative analysis

The content validity of the beta version was assessed in parallel for the English, German, and Arabic versions. This version contained a total of 118 items. Revisions were made based on two principles: 1. Changes that needed to be applied to the content of all three languages, affecting a total of 30 items. For example, two items were split into two separate items to allow for more precise impairment grading, leading to a total of 120 items. 2. Changes that were necessary in only one language to enhance clarity and ensure cultural adaptation, including the addition of culturally relevant details or examples.

In the Arabic version, it was needed to further clarify and improve the terminology of some items. For example, in the personal factors domain A01, all 30 participants deemed the third answer option inappropriate ("Please enter your gender: Female, Male, Diverse"), resulting in its removal. Similarly, in the Body Functions domain, 7 participants found that item H01 "Do you have problems with mood (e.g., experience intense mood swings (shifts) and self-image issues, rapid issues in mood in a relatively short period)?" was difficult to understand, suggesting a need for rephrasing. The majority of participants (26 subjects) found item H03 ("Do you have a problem with focusing your attention on one thing?") confusing due to a lack of time reference, suggesting the need for rephrasing or the addition of a duration component. For example, the question could be modified to: "If yes, please indicate how long you are typically able to maintain your focus on a single task or activity."

Content validity, quantitative analysis

Body Functions (BF) and Activity and Participation (AP)

Domains

Table 2 summarizes the content validity evaluation of 66 items within the BF and AP domains (in the range of H01 to H74). Percentages were classified into three groups: "No Reported Impairment," referring to a response of "0" on the Likert scale, "Reported Problems, Impairment or Difficulty (Mild to Profound)," referring to responses ranging from "1" to "4", and "Non-gradable items" (including responses marked as "I don't know", "Not Applicable", "Not required", or "Missing data"). For a more detailed classification, the responses of the "Reported Impairment or Difficulty (Mild to Profound)" group, ranging from 0 to 100%, are further divided into 4 subgroups 1) Low Prevalence (0%-19%), 2) Moderate Prevalence (20%-49%), 3) High Prevalence (50%-79%), and 4) Very High Prevalence (80%-100%).

The remaining eight items in the BF domain (H.41 to H.48) are developed to assess voice and speech impairments. Two participants with a history of stroke reported experiencing such impairments. For all other participants, responses to these items were recorded as "Not Required" in the collected database.

Environmental Factors (EF) Domain

Table 3 summarizes the content validity evaluation of the EF domain. For Items from 75 to 80, percentages were classified into three categories: "No Reported Support or Usefulness," "Reported Support or Usefulness (Mild to Complete)," and "Non-gradable items" (including responses marked as "I don't know", "Not Applicable", "Not required", or "Missing data.") For Items 81 to 86, percentages were classified into three categories: "No Reported Barriers," "Reported Barriers (Mild to Complete), and "Non-gradable items" (including responses marked as "I don't know", "Not Applicable", "Not required", or "Missing data." If a participant was a hearing aid user, the items H.87 to H.90 were recorded for their usefulness. For a more detailed classification, the responses of the "Reported or Usefulness or Support (Mild to Complete)" group, ranging from 0 to 100%, are further divided into 4 subgroups 1) Low Prevalence (0%-19%), 2) Moderate Prevalence (20%-49%), 3) High Prevalence (50%-79%), and 4) Very High Prevalence (80%-100%).

Outcome score

Three outcome scores – *hearing-related, non-hearing-related, and speech-perception* – were defined based on the outcome of a cross-sectional multicenter study involving 215 participants across Germany, the USA,

Table 2 Content Validity of of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool - Arabic among the Body Functions and Activity and Participation Items

Prevalence	Tool's Domain	Tool's Item(s)	ICF Code and Meaning
0-19%	F	H10	b250 – Taste Function
		H11	b255 – Smell Function
		H14	b280 – General
		H15	b280 – Pain - Head & Neck
20-49%	A, C, F, G	H8 & H9	b210 – Vision - Far & Near
		H12 & H13	b240 – Dizziness, Balance
		H16	b167 – Language Processing
		H17	b167 – Meaningful Message Processing
		H27	b2301 – Sound Discrimination
		H32	b2302 – Localization of Sound Source
50-79%	A, C, G	H62	d360S – Speech-Reading
		H1	b126 – Temperament & Personality
		H2	b134 – Sleep Function
		H3	d160 – Focusing Attention
		H7	b152 – Emotional Functions
		H5 & H6	b144 – Memory
		H19	b240 – Ear Pressure
		H20	b240 – Ear Irritation
		H23	b1560 – Auditory Perception
		H25	b2300 – Sound Detection
		H26 & H38	b2301 – Sound Discrimination
		H28, H29, H30 & H31	b2302 – Localization of Sound
		H33	b2303 – Lateralization of Sound
		H36	b1560 – Auditory Perception
		H39	b2304 – Speech Discrimination
		H49	d240 – Handling Stress
		H50	d710 – Basic Interpersonal Interaction
		H51	d750 – Informal Social Relationships
		H56	d355 – Discussion
		H57	d310 – Receiving Spoken Messages
H58	d780 – Family Relationships		
H59	d910 – Community Life		
H60	d920 – Recreation & Leisure		
H61	d720 – Complex Interpersonal Interaction		
H63	d830 – School Education		
H64	d220 – Multitasking		
H72	d360 – Carrying a Phone Call		
H73	d3503 – Conversation with One Person		
H74	d115 – Listening		

Table 2 (continued)

Prevalence	Tool's Domain	Tool's Item(s)	ICF Code and Meaning
80-100%	A, D, E, F	H4	b140 – Attention
		H18	b240 – Tinnitus
		H21, H22, H35, & H37	b1560 – Auditory Perception
		H24	b2300 – Sound Detection
		H34 & H40	b2301 – Sound Discrimination
		H52	d730 – Relating with Strangers
		H53	d740 – Family Relationship
		H54 & H55	d750 – Informal Social Relationship
		H65	d830 – School Education
		H66	d220 – Multitasking
		H67, H69, & H70	d3503 – Conversation with One Person
H68 & H71	d3504 – Conversation with Many People		

A) Auditory Processing Functionality, C) Listening and Communication Functionality, D) Interpersonal Interaction Functionality and Infrastructure Accessibility, E) Social Determinants and Infrastructure Compatibility, F) Other Sensory Integration Functionality, and G) Cognitive Functionality

Table 3 Content Validity of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool - Arabic among the Environmental Items

Prevalence	Tool's Domain	Tool's Item(s)	ICF Code and Meaning
0-19 %	None	None	None
20-29 %	B ^a	H87, H88, H89, & H90	e125 – Products and technology for communication
30-49 %	None	None	None
50-79 %	B	H82	e240 – Light
		H81	e150 – Design, Construction, and Building
80-100 %	E	H85 & H86	e2501 – Sound Quality
		H75	e460 – Social Attitudes
		H76	e410 – Individual Attitudes of Immediate Family
		H77	e310/e320 – Immediate Family and Friends
		H78	e580 – Health Services, Systems, and Policies
		H79	e355 – Health Professional
		H83	e2500 – Sound Intensity
H84	e2501 – Sound Quality		
H80	e535 – Communication Services, Systems, & Policies		

B) Sound Quality Compatibility, and E) Social Determinants and Infrastructure Compatibility

^a Hearing Aid Usefulness

and Egypt. The *hearing-related score* comprises three domains: A) Auditory Processing Functionality, B) Sound Quality Compatibility, and C) Listening and Communication Functionality. The *non-hearing-related score*

includes four domains: D) Interpersonal Interaction Functionality and Infrastructure Accessibility, E) Social Determinants and Infrastructure Compatibility, F) Other

Fig. 1 The distribution of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic scores is separated based on the PTA and hearing aid provision

Sensory Integration Functionality, and G) Cognitive Functionality [21, 22].

All three scores were defined on a scale from 0 to 10, with a score of 0 indicating that all included items were answered with a “No”. For detailed information on the score calculation, please refer to [22]. Descriptive statistics for the three outcome scores showed that the hearing-related score ranged from 0.07 to 7.99, with a mean of 3.68 (SD=2.15). Similarly, the speech-perception score ranged from 0.08 to 8.39, with a mean of 3.78 (SD=2.15). The non-hearing-related score had a narrower range (0.95 to 6.07) and a slightly lower mean of 3.21 (SD=1.09).

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic scores, categorized by PTA and hearing aid provision (normal hearing, hearing-impaired unaided, and aided groups). The hearing-related scores showed a broad overall distribution, reflecting variability across participants. The aided-impaired group exhibited a more compact distribution with higher scores compared to the unaided-impaired group, suggesting a potential benefit of hearing aid use. The normal hearing group displayed a wider spread, indicating individual differences in performance among those with normal hearing. The speech perception scores also demonstrated considerable variability, with the presence of outliers. The aided-impaired group had a higher median score than the unaided-impaired group, reinforcing the potential

advantage of amplification in speech perception. The normal hearing group showed a moderate distribution, with scores clustering toward the lower end, indicating some variation in performance within this group. The non-hearing-related score was more tightly clustered across all groups, suggesting lower variability. However, outliers were observed in some groups. The normal hearing group exhibited the widest distribution, indicating greater variation in performance compared to both the aided and unaided-impaired groups. Overall, these findings suggest that hearing aids may enhance performance in hearing-related and speech-perception tasks.

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of responses for each functional domain using box plots based on the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic scores. The variability across domains reflects differences in participants’ perceptions and experiences. Hearing-related domains, notably Sound Quality Compatibility and Hearing Aid Benefits, show higher median scores and tighter ranges, suggesting greater consistency in responses. Conversely, non-hearing-related domains like Cognitive Functionality and Other Sensory Integration Functionality exhibit wider dispersion and multiple outliers, pointing to individual differences or possible variations in interpretation. Extreme values in several items underscore the need for further analysis of response patterns and potential refinement of these items to enhance clarity and uniformity.

Fig. 2 The distribution of responses to the items of each label over all the participants

Table 4 Reliability Statistics

HEAR-COMMAND-Arabic Tool Domains	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Body Functions excluding 41–48	40	0.94
Activity Limitation and Participation Domain	26	0.90
All items excluding 41–48 and 87–90 ^a	78	0.97

^a Based on all 52 subjects

Reliability

The reliability of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients across various domains. The results indicated high internal consistency for the Body Functions Domain, excluding items 41–48, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.94. The Activity Limitation and Participation Domain also showed high internal consistency, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.90. Additionally, when considering all items, excluding items 41–48 and 87–90, the overall Cronbach’s Alpha across 52 subjects was 0.97, reflecting excellent internal consistency. Further details can be found in Table 4.

Discussion

This paper presents the translation and content validation of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic, designed to enhance clinicians’ ability to gather meaningful data on everyday functioning relevant to HL. By ensuring linguistic and cultural appropriateness through rigorous qualitative and quantitative validation, this tool provides

a comprehensive assessment of HL and its broader functional relationship with communication and conversational abilities. Notably, the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic represents the first significant advancement in hearing-related assessment within the Arab world. With its comprehensive, ICF-aligned structure, it has the potential to replace or complement existing tools, providing a better cultural adaptation and a more holistic assessment of both hearing and non-hearing-related factors [17].

The reliability of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic shows strong internal consistency across key domains, the Body Functions Domain, and the Activity Limitation and Participation Domain. Overall, Cronbach’s Alpha across 52 subjects, excluding items 41–48 and 87–90, was 0.97, confirming excellent internal consistency. These results suggest that the tool is reliable for assessing functioning and disability in Arabic-speaking individuals with HL. Future studies should further explore the validity and impact of the excluded items to ensure a comprehensive assessment.

By the time of submission, the availability of an online version significantly enhances accessibility, allowing healthcare providers and researchers in various settings to easily incorporate it into clinical practice. Furthermore, its potential integration with electronic medical records and hospital management systems could streamline its use, increasing efficiency and extending its applicability across a wide range of healthcare environments [17].

A key observation from the results is the varying degree of representation among different functional components. Items related to *sensory integration functionality*, such as taste, smell, and pain perception, exhibited the lowest prevalence (0%-19%), suggesting that these aspects may not be central to hearing and communication assessment. While these functions contribute to overall sensory experiences, their limited presence in the tool implies a focus on auditory-specific impairments rather than broader multisensory integration.

In contrast, the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic effectively captures key components that influence communication abilities and daily participation, which are critical for evaluating hearing-related functioning. Our findings showed that *cognitive and auditory processing functionalities* showed moderate prevalence (50%-79%), encompassing attention, memory, emotional functions, and auditory perception. These findings align with existing literature, which underscores the importance of cognitive and emotional factors in auditory rehabilitation and communication success [18, 25–28]. The inclusion of these domains in the tool reinforces its relevance in assessing not only hearing function but also the cognitive and emotional challenges faced by individuals with hearing difficulties. Noteworthy, the ICF has been widely applied in the literature to describe and differentiate the broad implications of hearing and cognitive functions on communication, particularly in the context of an aging population [29]. The benefit of addressing the dual *cognitive and auditory processing functionalities* among audiology patients is of increasing clinical importance for all clinicians working with adults and older adults. This integrated approach can provide a more holistic view of an individual's communication abilities, enabling the development of more comprehensive intervention strategies that consider both cognitive and auditory factors, thereby enhancing treatment outcomes and improving overall patient care.

Further, items within the highest prevalence category (80%-100%) encompass key elements of *auditory processing and social interaction*, such as sound detection and discrimination, tinnitus perception, interpersonal relationships, and communication across various environments. These findings underscore the significance of incorporating social determinants into hearing and tinnitus assessments. The robust presence of these items highlights that the tool extends beyond traditional hearing measures, capturing the broader impact of hearing impairments on everyday life. This aligns with the ICF model's emphasis on functioning and participation, further reinforcing the tool's holistic approach to assessment. A marked finding in our study is the lower reported difficulty in interpersonal interaction

functionality and infrastructure accessibility in Egypt (38%) compared to the USA and Germany (close to 90%). This discrepancy could reflect sociocultural differences in how HL is perceived and accommodated. In many Arab societies, strong social support networks may mitigate the perceived impact of HL, whereas Western societies often rely on individual accommodations. Further analysis is needed to determine whether environmental factors, such as workplace accessibility and public infrastructure, contribute to these differences.

Furthermore, the content validity analysis of the environmental items provides valuable insights into the external factors influencing hearing and communication. The results demonstrate a strong focus on *social determinants, infrastructure compatibility, and sound quality*, all of which are critical considerations for individuals with hearing impairments. The strongest representation (80%-100%) was found in social determinants and infrastructure compatibility, underscoring the critical role of social attitudes, family support, healthcare systems, and policies in shaping hearing-related outcomes [30]. The inclusion of items on family, friends, and healthcare professionals emphasizes the importance of interpersonal and systemic support in managing hearing impairments. Additionally, incorporating items addressing communication services and public policies reflects the tool's recognition of the broader societal and policy-level factors that impact accessibility and inclusion for individuals with hearing difficulties. Sound quality compatibility (50–79%) emerged as a significant factor, with items related to light, building design, and sound quality contributing to environmental accessibility. These findings align with research highlighting the importance of room acoustics, lighting, and spatial design in speech perception, particularly for individuals with HL only or with HL and tinnitus. The inclusion of these items suggests that the tool effectively captures key contextual factors that either facilitate or hinder communication, further solidifying its utility for comprehensive audiologic assessment.

Additionally, these findings highlight potential areas for further refinement. While the tool demonstrates strong validity in core auditory functions, the lower prevalence of certain *sensory integration items* (e.g., *balance and vestibular functions*) suggests a possible gap in assessing broader sensory-motor interactions in individuals with hearing impairments. Future research could explore the inclusion of additional items related to vestibular function and spatial awareness, particularly given the established link between hearing loss and balance disorders [17, 18].

Our findings also align with previous research that hypertension and diabetes mellitus are the most frequently reported conditions in Germany and the USA among individuals with HL. Establishing a link between chronic conditions and hearing loss may motivate earlier intervention. If individuals with high scores recognize their increased risk of hearing-related impairments, they may be more inclined to seek early treatment. This could lead to better long-term outcomes and increased use of hearing aids and rehabilitation services in the Arab world.

In our cohort, the 20%-29% value for *Environment and Hearing Aid Usefulness* (H87/H88/H89/H90 – e125 *Products and Technology for Communication*) may seem low; however, this is due to 78.8% of participants being non-hearing aid users, who were not required to respond to this section. Therefore, the reported percentage is based on responses from only 11 hearing aid users, not the entire sample. Importantly, the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic can also evaluate hearing aid benefits. All hearing aid users rated their device's benefit between 1 and 4, with none reporting no (0) benefit. The mean scores for the four related items ranged from 3.1 to 3.5 out of 4, demonstrating that participants found their hearing aids highly beneficial.

One potential benefit of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic is its ability to provide individuals with concrete scores that quantify their hearing and non-hearing-related aspects. This objective measure may encourage individuals to seek treatment earlier, particularly in settings where HL is often neglected until it becomes severe. A high score may serve as a wake-up call, prompting individuals to consult audiologists and explore interventions such as hearing aids. Additionally, healthcare providers can use these scores to counsel patients on the importance of early intervention, potentially improving overall treatment outcomes.

The overall findings reinforce the idea that hearing and communication challenges extend beyond individual impairment to external and societal factors. Clinicians and policymakers can leverage this tool to identify and address environmental barriers, ensuring that individuals with hearing impairments receive appropriate accommodation and support. By addressing multiple domains, the tool provides a multidimensional evaluation of hearing-related disability. This makes it a valuable resource for healthcare professionals aiming to design personalized intervention strategies that address both auditory and non-auditory challenges.

Several ICF-based tools have been adapted for use in Arab countries, particularly in the fields of rehabilitation and disability assessment, to explore cultural differences in participation and rehabilitation, providing valuable

insights into how disability is experienced in Arab societies [31, 32]. Comparing the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic with other ICF-based studies can help contextualize its findings and identify areas for improvement. Future studies should examine whether similar patterns emerge in other disability assessments and whether cultural factors influence the way individuals report their experiences.

Study limitations

The study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. One key limitation is the small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the results to the broader population. A larger sample size would provide more robust data and enhance the external validity of the tool's application.

Another limitation is the geographic scope, as the study was conducted exclusively in Egypt, limiting the applicability of the findings to other Arabic-speaking regions. The linguistic and cultural appropriateness of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic may vary across different Arab countries, and further validation studies in other regions would be beneficial to assess its cross-cultural applicability and relevance.

Additionally, the current study focused on individuals with hearing loss but did not specifically include those with cochlear implants or individuals with severe-to-profound hearing loss. Future research could explore the utility of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic among cochlear implant users and individuals with severe-to-profound HL, both within Egypt and in other Arab countries. This would help to further refine the tool and ensure it is sensitive to the unique needs and challenges faced by this specific group.

Conclusion

The HEAR-COMMAND Tool – Arabic serves as a comprehensive and multidimensional assessment instrument. Its content validity confirms its potential as a valuable tool for clinicians, researchers, and policymakers aiming to enhance hearing rehabilitation and accessibility. By addressing both individual and systemic challenges, the tool contributes to a more inclusive and functionally oriented approach to audiologic assessment and intervention. Grounded in ICF, this tool represents a significant advancement in hearing-related assessment within the Arab world.

Abbreviations

HL	Hearing Loss
MENA	Middle Eastern and North African
ICF	International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health

Authors' contributions

Tool Development & Refinement: Razan Alfakir, Mahmoud Hammady, Mohamed Abd Al-Ghaffar, and Mostafa Youssif. Subject Recruitment, Data Collection, and Initial Analysis: Mahmoud Hammady, Mohamed Abd Al-Ghaffar, and Mostafa Youssif. Data Curation & Analysis Review: Razan Alfakir and Tahereh Afghah. Manuscript Writing (Original Draft): Razan Alfakir and Tahereh Afghah. Final Review & Approval: All authors.

Funding

The HEAR-COMMAND Tool development and validation study: This study was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – Project ID: 352015383 – SFB 1330, C4. The funding was used in the study's design and the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data.

Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations**Ethics approval and consent to participate**

This study did not involve any experiments on humans or animals. The research protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Sohag University (registration number: Soh-Med-22–9-04). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Received: 31 March 2025 Accepted: 7 May 2025

Published online: 03 July 2025

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